

SULPHATION OF FATTY ACIDS. PART III. EFFECT OF CONCENTRATION OF SULPHURIC ACID ON OLEIC ACID AT HIGHER TEMPERATURE

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Sulphation of oleic acid was carried out by using H_2SO_4 of concentration ranging from 70.8% to 12% oleum in the proportion of 1 to 3 moles at 90° . Maximum sulphation and hydrolysis were observed when 85.5% H_2SO_4 reacted with oleic acid for 1 hour. 98.8% H_2SO_4 and 12% oleum gave sulphonates also. Unsaturation in the products was reduced to minimum and then it increased with the strength of sulphuric acid due to the dehydrating effect of concentrated acid on hydrolysed products formed.

Lewkowitsch¹ carried out sulphation of oleic acid at 5° with 92% sulphuric acid to 103% fuming acid, and found that the iodine number could not be reduced to zero. The proportion of stearo-lactone was increased when the reaction was carried out at 132° . Shukoff² patented the direct production of stearo-lactone by treating the theoretical amount of concentrated sulphuric acid with oleic acid at 70° to 80° and Clutterbuck³ published the method of isolation of this lactone. Burton and Byrne⁴ during their study on effect of various proportions of reactants on the composition of sulphated oleic acid, observed that sulphuric acid (98.8%) gave more of lactones, lactides and estolides at 50° than at 20° . They also reported the formation of sulphonates at 50° .

In the previous communication⁵ it was shown that the degree of sulphation of oleic acid in carbon tetrachloride increased with the concentration and molar ratio of sulphuric acid at 5° . The iodine value drop indicated the extent of reaction at the double bond and the fall in acidity of the reaction mixture gave the degree of sulphation.

Below 20° the reaction is mainly sulphation at the double bond, while at higher temperatures hydrolysis of the sulphuric ester is considerable and large amounts of hydroxy-acids and their derivatives are produced. The effect of concentration of sulphuric acid at 90° has been studied in the present work to determine the extent of sulphation, sulphonation and hydroxylation of oleic acid.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

About 10 g. of oleic acid was taken by a burette in a 250 ml. round-bottom flask fitted with ground glass condenser and heated on a water-bath. When oleic acid had attained the temperature of about 85° to 90°, calculated amount of H₂SO₄ in the proportion of three moles to one mole of oleic acid was added by the burette and kept on the water-bath at 90° ± 1° for 1 hour with occasional shaking. The resulting product was immediately washed by stirring with 250 ml. of 15% sodium sulphate solution and allowed to settle overnight. The product was separated and washed to remove unchanged H₂SO₄. After the final wash, the product was dried under vacuum. The experiments were carried out using 70.8%, 75.7%, 80.4%, 85.5%, 89.5%, 98.8% H₂SO₄ and 12% oleum. The products prepared by the last three concentrations required overnight settling for each wash, and they were viscous in nature. The yields of the products were about 10g. for 10g. of oleic acid.

TABLE I

Action of H₂SO₄ on oleic acid (N.V. 200.A ; I.V. 88.1) at 90° ± 1°.

Oleic acid : H₂SO₄ = 1 mole : 3 moles. Time of reaction = 1 hr.

Sample No.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Conc. of H ₂ SO ₄ added	70.8%	75.7%	80.4%	85.5%	89.5%	98.8%	12% Oleum
Amount of H ₂ SO ₄ added } (ml.) (on 100% pure basis) } (g.)	9.1	8.2	7.5	6.9	6.5	5.9	5.4
	10.49	10.49	10.49	10.26	10.26	10.42	10.42
I.V. of the product	83.9	76.1	49.6	40.0	43.6	46.9	48.5
Fall in I.V. (I)	4.2	11.7	38.5	48.1	44.5	41.2	39.6
Acid value of the product	185.3	175.2	142.9	124.3	112.8	153.3	137.8
Fall in acid value (A)	15.1	25.2	57.6	76.1	87.4	67.1	62.8
mg. of KOH equiv. to fall in I.V. } per g. of the product (B)* } }	18.6	51.2	170.2	212.6	196.7	182.2	175.1
Extent of hydrolysis (B-A)=(E)	3.5	26.4	112.6	136.5	109.3	115.1	112.5
Total -SO ₄ in mg. KOH per g. } of the product (T) } }	nil	nil	nil	22.0	17.3	18.1	26.6
Free hydroxy-acids († B-T)	9.3	25.8	85.1	84.3	81.0	79.0	60.9
-OSO ₃ H mg. of KOH per g. (S)	nil	nil	nil	21.4	17.2	11.4	14.9
-SO ₃ H mg. of KOH per g. (T-S)	nil	nil	nil	0.6	0.1	6.7	11.7
Lactones, lactides, α -estolides } (E-H)=(L) }	-5.8	0.6	27.5	52.2	28.3	36.1	51.6

$$B = \frac{I \times 56.1 \times 1000}{126.9 \times 100}$$

Acid values of the washed products were determined in the usual manner. Iodine values were determined by Rossenmund-Kuhnemann method, modified by Benham and Klee⁶. The total sulphate estimation by the Procter and Searle method, given by Burton and Byrne⁷, was modified in the following respects. The product was taken in a platinum dish, 50ml. of N/10-NaOH was added per gram, evaporated to dryness and then heated to 500°-550°

for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour in a muffle furnace. The ash was dissolved in distilled water to which 50ml. of $N/10\text{-H}_2\text{SO}_4$ was added, boiled, then cooled and titrated with $N/10\text{-KOH}$ solution using bromophenol blue as an indicator. The total sulphate (T) was calculated in terms of mg. of KOH per g. of the product. The sulphate group ($-\text{OSO}_3\text{H}$) was estimated by the A.L.C.A. provisional method as recommended by Burton⁷. In this method the excess of sulphuric acid produced by hydrolysis of the sulphate group was titrated with $N/2\text{-KOH}$ and a blank was also carried out to estimate the quantity of $1N$ sulphuric acid added for hydrolysis. The $-\text{OSO}_3\text{H}$ group (S) was calculated in terms of mg. of KOH per g. of the product. The difference between the total sulphate (T) and $-\text{OSO}_3\text{H}$ (S) gave the sulphonate ($-\text{SO}_3\text{H}$) group in terms of mg. of KOH per g. of the product. The results are recorded in Table I.

DISCUSSION

The drop in iodine values (Table I) shows that the main initial reaction is at the double bond which can be represented by the equation :

The amount of sulphuric esters (S) formed depends on the concentration of sulphuric acid used for sulphation. The samples No. 1, 2 and 3, prepared by 70.8%, 75.7% and 80.4% sulphuric acid, show that the sulphates formed initially are hydrolysed immediately, forming hydroxy-acids and their derivatives, whereas the products, prepared by reacting H_2SO_4 of 85.5% strength and above, show the formation of sulphates ($-\text{OSO}_3\text{H}$).

The total acidity (A) of the product is lower than that calculated from the fall in iodine value (B) indicating the extent of hydrolysis ($B-A = E$). The amount of hydroxy-acids can be calculated indirectly as the determination of hydroxyl value is difficult due to the complex nature of the products with free $-\text{COOH}$, $-\text{SO}_3\text{H}$ and $-\text{OSO}_3\text{H}$ groups. The amount of hydroxy-acids (H) has been computed from the difference in half the fall in iodine value and total sulphates (T). The number of free $-\text{COOH}$ groups present originally in oleic acid will partly be converted into lactones, lactides and estolides; the fall in acid value should give the amount of these condensed products. As the products contain $-\text{OSO}_3\text{H}$ and $-\text{SO}_3\text{H}$ groups, fall in acid value will not be a true representation of these condensed products. The amount of these products are obtained by subtracting hydroxy-acids (H) from the extent of hydrolysis (E). The maximum amounts of these compounds are found in samples No. 4 and 7.

The iodine values of the products decrease to the minimum (sample No. 4, I.V. 40) and then again increase with the strength of the reacting sulphuric acid. The sulphates ($-\text{OSO}_3\text{H}$) are formed at the double bond and are hydrolysed to hydroxy-acids which may undergo dehydration in

the presence of strong sulphuric acid and the double bond is reformed. *iso*Oleic acids in sulphated products have been reported by Riess⁸ and Lewkowitsch¹ at higher concentrations of sulphuric acid, even at lower temperatures. The increase in iodine values in samples No. 5 and 7 is due to the reformation of the double bond at higher concentrations of sulphuric acid. The sulphonates in samples No. 6 and 7 are increased because sulphuric acid may be reacting at the $-CH_2$ groups adjacent to the double bond.

The reaction products of sulphuric acid below 85.5% strength do not show presence of sulphates and sulphonates. However, there is increasing hydroxylation up to 80.4% strength due to the dilute acid. Maximum amount of sulphation is observed when 85.5% to 89.5% sulphuric acid is reacted with oleic acid for one hour; whereas 98.8% sulphuric acid to 12% oleum give sulphonates besides sulphates.

R E F E R E N C E S

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